

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of nitrogen and zinc on indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) concentration in roots and root production in wetland rice

M. A. Salam, Kerala Agricultural University, Cropping System Research Centre, Karamana 695002; and S.

Subramanian, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore 641003, India

IAA triggers meristematic activity and plant growth. A high IAA concentration in rice roots, especially at panicle initiation stage is indicative of high root production and activity and better crop performance.

We measured IAA concentration in rice roots at panicle initiation in relation to N and Zn nutrition at TNAU (11°N, 77°E and 427 m above sea level) during the southwest monsoon season (Jun-Sep) 1983. The factorial design combined 4 levels of N (0, 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha) and 2 levels of Zn (0 and 5.75 kg/ha). The soil contained 1.1% organic C, 196-9.5-200 ppm available NPK, 598 ppm total soil N, and 0.4 ppm DTPA extractable Zn. Test variety was IR20. The test field was laid out in a randomized block design with six replications.

N and Zn showed a synergistic interaction on IAA concentration in rice

roots. At 120 kg N/ha with Zn, IAA in roots was highest (462 µg/kg fresh root); at 120 kg N/ha without Zn, it was very low (281 µg/kg fresh root) (Table 1). IAA concentration was more or less the same at all levels of N without Zn.

Root weight increased with N increase up to 120 kg/ha at all growth stages (Table 2). Zn also increased root production at all stages. The coefficients of correlation of IAA concentration in rice roots with root dry weight at panicle initiation (0.55), root dry weight at flowering (0.51), and root dry weight at harvest (0.56) were significant and positive. □

Table 2. Root dry weight at different growth stages as influenced by levels of N and Zn.

	Root dry weight (t/ha)			
	Tillering	Panicle initiation	Flowering	Harvest
N level (kg/ha)				
0	0.4	0.8	0.9	1.1
60	0.5	0.9	1.1	1.2
90	0.5	1.2	1.3	1.4
120	0.7	1.4	1.6	1.7
LSD (0.05)	0.05	0.1	0.1	0.1
Zn level (kg/ha)				
0	0.5	1.0	1.1	1.3
5.75	0.6	1.2	1.3	1.4
LSD (0.05)	0.04	0.09	0.08	0.06

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Tissue test of rice plant nitrogen

A. B. Blakeney, G. D. Batten, and P. E. Bacon, Yanco Agricultural Institute, Yanco 2730; and M. R. Glennie Holmes, Agricultural Research Institute, Wagga Wagga 2650, New South Wales Department of Agriculture, Australia

In Australia, rice farmers dry-seed rice by drill sowing directly into a dry seedbed or by drilling into a closely grazed pasture. The crop is flooded 2-4 times before it reaches the 3- to 4-leaf stage, when a permanent flood is applied. Or, fields are permanently flooded with shallow water and pregerminated rice seed is dropped by airplane.

The recommended times for N fertilizer application are just before permanent flood and just after panicle initiation. If farmers are confident of the appropriate fertilizer rate, all or most is

applied before the permanent flood. If farmers are unsure of the appropriate fertilizer rates or if there is a risk of overfertilization or low-temperature sterility, one-half to two-thirds N is applied before permanent flood, the remainder at panicle initiation.

A critical management decision is the amount of N to apply at panicle initiation to achieve maximum yield.

We have developed a plant analysis test that can rapidly determine crop N status and estimate N topdressing needed. Whole shoot samples are cut at ground level at panicle initiation, quickly dried in a 700 W microwave oven (200 g fresh wt in 13-15 min), ground in a Cyclone mill to pass through a 1-mm screen, and analyzed for tissue N status by near infrared reflectance (NIR).

NIR gave an excellent correlation with traditional Kjeldahl N analysis (see figure). Preliminary results indicate that

Table 1. N-Zn interactions on rice root IAA content at panicle initiation.^a TNAU, India, 1983.

Zn level (kg/ha)	IAA content (µg/kg fresh root)				
	No N	N60	N90	N120	Mean
0	279	283	299	281	278
5.75	348	375	361	462	387
Mean	314	329	330	372	
	<i>LSD (0.05)</i>				
	N				15
	Zn				17
	N × Zn				35

^aN in kg/ha.

Relationship between NIR and the Kjeldahl methods of measuring rice shoot N status.

yield can be increased by topdressing N when plant N is below 1.5% at panicle initiation.

A 2- to 3-d analysis service is planned. Farmers will collect samples of their crops, dry them in domestic microwave ovens, and send the dry samples to a central laboratory. The laboratory will complete the analysis and advise the farmer on the amount of N fertilizer needed. □

Effect of source and rate of phosphorus on yield and yield attributes of rice

M. L. Gupta and R. C. Gautam, Agronomy Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, Nainital 263145, U.P., India

A field experiment was conducted during the wet season at the Crop Research Centre (29°N 79.3°E and 243.84 m altitude). The experimental field soil was Beni silty clay loam, fine-silty, mixed, hyperthermic, Aquic Hapludoll with pH 7.6, CEC 20 meq, 1.06% organic C, 20 kg available (Olsen) P/ha, and 196 kg available K/ha.

Five P sources—rock phosphate, single superphosphate, rock phosphate + superphosphate, rock phosphate + single superphosphate + pyrite, and

Grain yield and yield attributes of rice as influenced by source and rate of P. Nainital, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ²	Filled grains/panicle	1000 grain wt (g)	Unfilled grain (%)
<i>Source</i>					
Rock phosphate	4.4	205	104	25.4	18.4
Superphosphate	5.4	252	108	25.7	13.1
Rock phosphate + superphosphate	4.7	219	107	25.8	15.7
Rock phosphate + superphosphate + pyrite	4.8	227	108	25.6	14.3
Rock phosphate + pyrite	4.7	220	108	25.8	15.2
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.2	7	2	ns	0.6
<i>Rate (kg P/ha)</i>					
13	4.6	215	106	25.5	17.1
26	4.8	228	107	25.8	14.9
40	4.9	231	108	25.7	14.0
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.2	5	2	ns	0.5
Control	4.3	193	100	25.6	20.4
Mean	4.77	223	107	25.6	15.6

rock phosphate + pyrite—at 3 rates—13, 26, and 40 kg P/ha—in 16 combinations were compared. Mussoorie rock phosphate : pyrite and single superphosphate : Mussoorie rock phosphate were mixed in 1:3 ratio. Mussoorie rock phosphate (100 mesh) was applied on the basis of 7% total P (2% citrate soluble). Pyrite was mixed and applied 15 d before transplanting in dry soil.

Rice variety Pant Dhan 4 seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing at 2-3 seedlings/hill. The crop was fertilized with 120 kg N and 9 kg

Zn/ha. No K was applied.

Grain yield, panicles/m², and filled grains/panicle with single superphosphate were significantly higher than with all other sources of P (see table). Other sources were also significantly superior to rock phosphate alone in effect on yield and yield attributes. Percentage unfilled grains decreased significantly with single superphosphate but was significantly higher with rock phosphate than with any other source.

P significantly increased grain yield, panicles/m², and filled grains/panicle. □

Effect of modified urea on rice yield

S. V. Subbaiah and S. K. Sharma, Agronomy Department, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, Andhra Pradesh, India

We studied the effect of an experimental coating material on N fertilizer use efficiency under lowland conditions during 1987 wet season. The coating material is a nonhydrous free-flowing liquid with a mild characteristic odor. The active principles that exert a nitrification regulatory effect are terpenoids and flavonoids compounded with certain polysaccharides and aldehydes.

The soil is a Vertisol with pH 8.4, CEC 50 meq/100 g soil, 0.1% total N (modified Kjeldahl method), and 6 ppm available P (Olsen's method). The experimental field was fertilized with 17.5 kg P and 33 kg K/ha at final puddling and 58 kg N/ha per treatment.

N fertilizers used were prilled urea (PU), large granule urea (LGU), and urea supergranule (USG). One percent of the experimental material and 5% neem cake powder were used to coat the modified urea materials.

Coated PU, LGU, and USG (hand placed 7 d after transplanting [DT]) with or without the new coating increased grain yield significantly over PU applied as standard split (2/3 basal, 1/3 at panicle initiation) (see table).